

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CRAFT SMANSHIP IN SETTAR B AHLULZADE CREATION ISSUES

*Mammadov M.
Ganja State University*

Abstract

This is a well-known brush master of Azerbaijan. It is dedicated to the artistic issues observed in the work of the people's artist Sattar Bahlulzade. The 34-year period of artistic research, which included portrait, landscape and still life genres in the artist's work, was rich in research. This manifested itself primarily in the performance of works of different genres with different artistic interpretations. In this sense, it should be noted that the artist's handwriting was changed several times. This is also confirmed by the fact that the artist's artistic heritage was expressed in realistic handwriting in the forties of the last century, lyrical in the fifties, laconic-generalized in the sixties, and finally, in the seventies, full of expression

Keywords: art, creativity, craftsmanship, aesthetics, good, tradition.

The rich artistic heritage of Sattar Bahlulzadeh (1909-1974), a famous brush master and People's Artist, who has a unique place in the 20th century Azerbaijani fine art, is notable for its variety of genres and executions. In other words, the numerous paintings created by him in portrait, landscape and still-life genres are eye-catching primarily because of the color solution that can make the viewer emotional. It is possible to witness the periodic renewal of his attitude to color and performance in his 34-year-long work. Although this kind of script evolution happened several times, the audience was able to recognize the creative "I" of Sattar Bahlulzade every time. It is for this reason that he is known as a tireless and unique singer of Azerbaijani nature.

By following the work of the famous artist in chronological order, which consists of several stages, it is possible to clarify the unique features of the artistry displayed by him in the creation of these works of various genres. It is possible to observe Sattar Bahlulzade's handwriting, which meets the aesthetics of primary and more academic painting, in the paintings he created in the 1940s. It is possible to refer to the works "Babak Uprising" and "Defense of Bezz Castle", as well as "Portrait of Gubali Fatali Khan" and "Calligrapher Mirali Tabrizi", which he painted as diploma work. In the color layer of these paintings, formed by harmonious colors, the figure and individual details that make up the composition are mainly realistic.

After that, the artist's close acquaintance with Absheron allows him to reveal aesthetic points that may seem interesting to the viewer in the harsh nature of this place at first glance. This causes the young artist's interest in the landscape genre to become even more serious. His visit to the Guba region at that time and the rich descriptive materials he collected here allow him to create beautiful landscapes.

After returning to Baku, he exhibited those paintings at exhibitions organized in the capital in 1947-1953 and won great audience sympathy. "Gudyalchay coast", "Gudyalchay valley", "The road to Gizbanovsh", "Spring song", "Green carpet", "Among the gardens", "Amsar gardens" etc. his works are like this. In these scenes, the artist was not satisfied with present-

ing what he saw in nature as it is, but tried to add a lyrical-emotional spirit to each motif. As a result, natural motifs, which have become ordinary in the eyes of many, have become more attractive and well-maintained.

The result of Sattar Bahlulzade's creative trips to Karabakh and Lankaran in the fifties was also successful, and he was able to exhibit new possibilities of his artistic potential by adding a realistic-romantic spirit to the scenes he created. The painting "Evening on the Caspian" painted by the artist in 1959 can be considered a starting point in the direction of changing his known handwriting. The most remarkable aspect of the work is the perceptible thinning of the color layer on the canvas, creating the impression that the laconic colors are painted with watercolors. Such a new manner, i.e., relatively little hearing of the "traces" of the eye, gave the image an eye-catching transparency, but did not prevent it from exhibiting its known capacity for attributes of various scales. In this sense, in "Evening on the Caspian" at the same time, the seagulls in the foreground are as elegant as the oil rigs in the background are, on the contrary, magnificent and large-scale. This kind of approach becomes a unique, characteristic artistic-aesthetic merit for the artist's work in later years. In other words, this kind of artistic approach serves as a reliable tool for the author of the works to create an image. Sattar Bahlulzade's "Beauty of the Caspian", "Land's Dream", "Kepaz's Tears", "Through the Field", "Spring in Mughan", "At the Foot of Bozdag", "Summer Evening", "Gülüstan" created by Sattar Bahlulzade in the 1960s. it is possible to be sure of this in the example of the tableaux. Although the spatial concreteness is not clearly felt in these works, which are the results of the artist's impressions from the most diverse corners of the republic, it is undeniable that each of them rises to the level of an almost generalized image of the land of Azerbaijan.

The artistic interpretation of Sattar Bahlulzade's understanding of nature, based on classical realism, took place in the second half of the sixties and the beginning of the seventies. The paintings created by the famous landscape artist in the mid-sixties are of special interest due to the extraordinary richness of the color

layer - the images created from different shades of colors. It is possible to witness the high artistry of the artist in these amazing landscapes created by the intersection of countless shades of color. Undoubtedly, such emotive scenes expressing different times of the day could be created only thanks to the continuous observations made in those places. It is impossible not to be impressed by Sattar Bahlulzade's skillful play in "Bazardüzü", "Shahnabad", "The Tale of Azerbaijan", "Ancient Flames of Surakhani" and other paintings covering that period.

One of the qualities that confirm the uniqueness of Sattar Bahlulzadeh's craftsmanship is related to his attitude to light and shadow. If we look at his creativity, we can see the successful results of this persistent attitude to "shadowlessness" in his works, large and small. Although the artist could not completely avoid this in the period of his creativity up to the sixties, in the later stage he almost continuously achieved the shadowlessness of artistic images, in other words, the realization of the image directly with the closeness and contrast of

colors, and achieved a convincing and impressive appearance. The basis of this kind of expressive artistic interpretation is, first of all, giving a modern look to the ancient traditions of miniature style. This unique aesthetic of painting can be found in "Dadegunesh", "Lazaman's waterfalls", "Singing mountains", "Shamakhi vineyards", "Blue fairy tale", "Absheron still life" and several other works created by the artist in the last three to four years of his life. . In our opinion, it would be logical to consider the artist's high level of performance throughout his work as the result of his creative attitude to classical painting and its artistic and technical possibilities.

References

1. Salamzadeh A., Rzayev N., Karimov K.A., Efendiyev R., Habibov N. Art of Azerbaijan. Baku, 1992.344 p.
2. Habibov N. Azerbaijani Soviet painting. Baku, 1966.188 p.
3. Aliyev Z. Sanatin Majnunuu. Baku, 2009.395 p.
4. Rahimli I. Sattar world. Baku. 1990. 170 p.